

SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS' MOTIVATION TOWARD SCIENCE LEARNING AND SCIENCE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the levels of motivation of students in learning science and determined the relationship of students' motivation toward science learning and their science academic performance. The respondents of the study were 87 Grade 11 students at Calawitan National High School, who were enrolled during the School Year 2023-2024. The researchers utilized a descriptive correlational research design to measure the relationship of science motivation toward science learning and science academic performance. The data were gathered through the use of Students Motivation Toward Science Learning (SMTSL)/questionnaire that was adapted from Tuan et al. (2005). The questionnaire was composed of statements divided into six (6) sub-categories namely; self-efficacy, active learning strategies, science learning value, performance goal, achievement goal and learning environment stimulation. The collected data were analyzed using the statistical software Jamovi and interpreted using descriptive statistics and Pearson r moment correlation. Results showed that students agreed that they are motivated in learning science in terms of active learning strategies ($M=3.57$), science learning value ($M=3.55$), achievement goal ($M=3.87$) and learning environment stimulation ($M=3.52$) while they gave no opinion about self-efficacy ($M=2.91$) and performance goal ($M=3.04$) which both contained negative statements. Also, it was found out that students' motivation toward science learning and science academic performance have a significant relationship ($r = 0.270^*$; p -value = 0.011) it means that as the students' motivation toward science learning increases, their science academic performance will become higher and

vice versa. Students who are motivated in learning science tend to have higher science academic performance.

Keywords: *students' motivation toward science learning, science academic performance, active learning strategies, science learning value, achievement goal, learning environment stimulation, self-efficacy, performance goal*

INTRODUCTION

Science education has been considered as one of the most important academic disciplines in schools because of its practical application, scientific knowledge, broad concept and its relevance to the students' lives (Shana & Abulibdeh, 2020). It offers them the opportunity to increase their overall understanding of how things work through the use of critical thinking and analysis of various scientific concepts. However, science as a subject in school has always presented a challenge to both teachers and students.

The Philippine education report of 2023 stated by Philippine Business for Education (2023) recognizes the urgent needs of the learners and educational systems especially in the field of the learners when it comes to their interests and motivation in learning, due to the COVID pandemic in 2019 and this has significantly impacted the lives of the learners when it comes to learning. As stated by Mardianti (2021), interests are depleting overtime because of lack of resource materials, lack of technological resources and proper exposure to learning environments due to the COVID pandemic. Thus, in the case of the PISA results in 2022 resulting in a devastating 3rd to the last rankings when it comes to levels of proficiency in particular in the field of science.

In addition, Salanga and Bernardo (2016) stated that Senior High School Filipino students face struggles due to a lack of motivation. Reasons include beliefs and attitudes about themselves and the subject, teacher competencies, and distractions from peers and family. Teachers have to primarily engage and motivate their students in learning science. Even though engagement does not necessarily result in understanding, especially when it comes to the case of learning science, engaging and motivating students in science is a prerequisite for understanding (Hadzigeorgiou & Schulz, 2019).

According to Njua (2020), it is difficult to meet the learning objectives of a particular course or field of study without motivation. The core of effective teaching is dependent on motivation. Since promoting lifelong learning is the main goal of all education, motivation should be viewed as the main tool for helping students succeed in the sciences. In order to encourage students to pursue interests in science, they need to be internally and extrinsically motivated. Albalate et al. (2018) claimed that without the motivation, surface learning or simply memorization will happen, which will not lead to a proper understanding of essential concepts of science. It is essential that students' motivation towards science learning among the students be assessed (L & H, 2018). As Mauliya et al. (2020) asserted that lack of motivation in students caused poor academic performance.

With the aforementioned articles and studies, the researchers are aiming to know a deeper understanding of the situation, considering the k-12 curriculum and the new 21st century learners. This study aims to assess the Senior High School student's motivation toward science learning as self-efficacy, active learning strategies, science learning value, performance goal, achievement goal, and learning environment stimulation.

Review of Related Literature and Studies

Science learning includes many factors that are the determinants of science learning quality and process (Chan & Norlizah, 2017). The result of the study conducted by Rana et al. (2015) pointed out that motivation towards learning is an important contributor in determining achievement of the students. There are six separate sub constructs that make up the multidimensional construct of motivation. To differing degrees, these structures influence the determination of learning motivation. The performance goal for example is the awareness among the students about what is being expected of them is a most prominent determinant of motivation to learn. In performance goal learning, students are not just involved in science learning and then expect recognition from other people or attention from their teachers. It is more in the direction of what students expect after they study science. It encourages them to engage in science learning (Nasir et al., 2023).

Key findings of Chan and Norlizah (2017) revealed that students' motivation towards science learning have a significant relation to students' science achievement. The findings showed that students who have moderate motivation to learn science have mid-low achievement in science. If students are not driven, they will probably not learn much and will typically find teaching difficult and irritating.

In addition, highly motivated students will probably learn quickly and make any class enjoyable (Filgona et.al., 2020). Self-regulation is very important for managing self-behaviour or motivation, which is essential for a student's educational achievement (Caruth,2018). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation can also affect the behavior of learners thus affecting their academic performance of the student's when it comes to science subjects (Tokan & Imakulata,2019).

Teachers aim to have a generation of successful students personally and academically. However, various uncontrolled factors can hinder this progress. One way to address this is to empower students' non-cognitive attributes. Therefore, learning in the classroom transitions to student-centered learning, where the main responsibility for progress is on the student. However, if students have destructive learning goals, a low perception of their capabilities, a short interest in the academic task, and limited effort, their learning outcomes will suffer (Alhadabi & Karpinski, 2020).

This study was anchored in the theory of Abraham Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs and Theory of Motivation, which indicates the fundamental basic needs of humans, he proposed that motivation is the result of a person's attempt in fulfilling five basic needs: physiological, safety, social, esteem and self-actualization. Maslow posited that human

motivation arises out of a motivation to progress through this hierarchy of needs. Maslow represented his theory pictorially as a pyramid, similar to the food pyramid, with the bottom representing the base and the most basic level. Once a person satisfies one level of needs, Maslow suggests they then become motivated to reach the next level.

Conceptual Framework

The paradigm included the relationship between the factors affecting the students' motivation toward science learning and academic performance.

Figure 1

Paradigm of the Study

Figure 1 shows the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The independent variables were the factors affecting students' motivation toward science learning: self-efficacy; active learning strategies; science learning value; performance goal; achievement goal and learning environment stimulation. The dependent variable was the academic performance. It was hypothesized in this study that students' motivation toward science learning has a significant relationship on students' academic performance as indicated by the directional orientation of the arrowhead.

Research Questions

This study aims to describe the Senior High School student's motivation toward science learning and academic performance at Calawitan National High School.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following research questions:

1. How may the student's motivation toward science learning be described in terms of:
 - 1.1. self - efficacy;

- 1.2. active learning strategies;
 - 1.3. science learning value;
 - 1.4. performance goal;
 - 1.5. achievement goal; and
 - 1.6. learning environment stimulation?
2. How may the students' academic performance in science be described?
 3. Is there a significant relationship between students' motivation toward science learning and science academic performance?
 4. Based on the result of the study, what intervention program can be developed to support the student's science performance?

Hypothesis

This study was guided and tested the hypothesis below:

Students' motivation toward science learning has no significant relationship on their science academic performance.

Significance of the Study

This study will help the students to better assess and understand their learning performance in science for self-improvement. This may serve as a source of information about how the various school factors and teacher factors influenced their learning performance in science. For teachers, this will serve as a valuable guide for them to help the students improve their knowledge, understanding and skills in science. It will also serve as a basis for improving instructional materials that still guarantee the quality of education. The result of this study will serve as a guide and reference for the administrators to have a basis in adjusting school policies and systems for students to help them become efficient learners. As a result, it can improve student's learning performance especially in science and even their performance outside school. The conducted study will further open doors for future researchers to refine and expand studies in relation to how motivation affects students' science learning and academic performance. This may serve as a source of information about the identified factors that influenced students' science learning and performance.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized descriptive correlational research design. This type of research design is used to understand the relationship between two or more variables. In this study, the researchers aimed to describe and determine the relationship between students' motivation on science learning and academic performance. According to Aprecia et al. (2021), descriptive correlational research design describes the variables and measures the extent of the relationships that occur between and among the variables.

Respondents and Sampling

Simple random sampling technique was utilized in selecting the student-respondents from the reported total Grade 11 Enrolment in the Senior High School Program. The researchers used the Raosoft sample size calculator in calculating the appropriate sample size for the study. The mentioned formula was used to obtain the needed sample size for the student-respondents in this study. The researchers determined the sample size for student-respondents based on the total of 111 Grade 11 enrollees of Calawitan National High School with a margin of error equivalent to 5% and a confidence level of 95%.

By applying the formula, the researchers determined the total number of respondents who will represent the population. This resulted in a total of 87 student-respondents among Grade 11 students of Calawitan National High School.

Instrumentation

In order to answer the problems provided, quantitative data were gathered using a survey questionnaire. The questionnaire "Students' Motivation Toward Science Learning" (SMTSL) was adapted from Tuan et al. (2005) to describe and measure students' motivation toward science learning. The questionnaire was composed of six subsections such as self-efficacy, active learning strategies, science learning value, performance goal, achievement goal, and learning environment stimulation which was rated using a scale of 4.21 – 5.00 – Strongly agree (5), 3.41 – 4.20 – Agree (4), 2.61 – 3.40 – No opinion (3), 1.81 – 2.60 – Disagree (2) and 1.00 – 1.80 – Strongly disagree (1). Cronbach alpha for the entire questionnaire was 0.89; for each scale, alpha ranged from 0.70 to 0.89. Findings of the study confirmed the validity and reliability of the SMTSL questionnaire (Tuan et al., 2005). The science academic performance of the respondents was gathered from the school record of Calawitan National High School through their adviser.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before the administration of survey questionnaire, the researchers first requested approval from the school principal to randomly selected Grade 11 students in Calawitan National High School as respondents for the study. Upon receiving the approved letter, coordination with the class advisers of Grade 11 students of the aforementioned school was done for the schedule of data collection. The researchers administered the questionnaire through Google Forms. In the administration of survey questionnaire and the respondents were allotted a 10-minute timeframe to complete the questionnaire. The data for science academic performance was collected through the class advisers.

The respondents in the study were informed that their involvement was entirely voluntary and they had the freedom to withdraw from participation at any time. The survey was also anonymous and in order to protect respondents' identities, no personal information was disclosed. Additionally, they were informed that all information gathered would be used exclusively to complete the study and that it will be completely deleted from the researchers' laptop upon completing the study.

Data Analysis

The researchers used a statistical software jAMOVl for the analysis and interpretation of the collected data. The jAMOVl software was found to be simple, flexible and easy to learn with very sophisticated analytical capacity.

Descriptive statistics such as mean was used to describe students' motivation toward science learning and their science academic performance. To test the hypothesis if students' motivation toward science learning has a significant relationship on science academic performance Pearson r moment correlation was utilized.

RESULTS

This chapter deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of the data collected and the results of the statistical treatment employed in the study with the purpose of determining the relationship between science motivation toward science learning and science academic performance of Grade 11 students of Calawitan National High School, Calawitan, San Idefonso, Bulacan.

Table 1. Self-efficacy

Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
1. Whether the science content is difficult or easy, I am sure that I can understand it	3.64	1.01	Agree
2. I am not confident about understanding difficult science concepts. (-)	2.93	0.950	No Opinion
3. I am sure that I can do well on science tests	3.61	0.969	Agree
4. No matter how much effort I put in, I cannot learn science. (-)	2.31	0.893	Disagree
5. When science activities are too difficult, I give up or only do the easy parts. (-)	2.80	1.09	No Opinion
6. During science activities, I prefer to ask other people for the answer rather than think for myself. (-)	2.69	1.09	No Opinion
7. When I find the science content difficult, I do not try to learn it (-)	2.40	0.994	Disagree
TOTAL	2.91	0.487	No Opinion

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)
2.61 – 3.40	No Opinion (NO)
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)

The table shows the students' science motivation toward science learning in terms of self-efficacy. The calculated total mean for self - efficacy is (M=2.91) with a standard

deviation of 0.487 which is interpreted as “No Opinion”. Since majority of the items in this category were negative statements, it means that respondents believed in their capacity to perform well in science. The students can still understand the science concept whether it is difficult or not and they are sure that they can do well on science tests.

Table 2. Active Learning Strategies

Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
1. When learning new science concepts, I attempt to understand them.	3.83	0.991	Agree
2. When learning new science concepts, I connect them to my previous experiences.	3.46	0.887	Agree
3. When I do not understand a science concept, I find relevant resources that will help me	3.56	0.997	Agree
4. When I do not understand a science concept, I would discuss it with the teacher or other students to clarify my understanding.	3.60	1.04	Agree
5. During the learning processes, I attempt to make connections between the concepts that I learn.	3.49	0.951	Agree
6. When I make a mistake, I try to find out why.	3.61	1.06	Agree
7. When I meet science concepts that I do not understand, I still try to learn them.	3.51	1.02	Agree
8. When new science concepts that I have learned conflict with my previous understanding, I try to understand why.	3.39	0.867	No Opinion
TOTAL	3.57	0.796	Agree

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)
2.61 – 3.40	No Opinion (NO)
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)

The table shows the students’ science motivation towards science learning in terms of active learning strategies. Majority of the respondents agreed on the statements resulting to a total mean of (M= 3.57, SD=0.796) interpreted as “Agree”. It means that the students engage themselves in various learning strategies to construct new knowledge based on their previous understanding of science concepts.

However, the student gave no opinion (M= 3.39, SD= 0.867) in the statement in item number 8 which is “*When new science concepts that I have learned conflict with my previous understanding, I try to understand why.*”

Table 3. Science Learning Value

Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
1. I think that learning science is important because I can use it in my daily life.	3.62	1.22	Agree
2. I think that learning science is important because it stimulates my thinking.	3.39	1.10	No Opinion
3. In science, I think that it is important to learn to solve problems.	3.67	0.936	Agree
4. In science, I think it is important to participate in inquiry activities.	3.51	1.08	Agree
5. It is important to have the opportunity to satisfy my own curiosity when learning science	3.55	1.13	Agree
TOTAL	3.55	0.932	Agree

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)
2.61 – 3.40	No Opinion (NO)
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)

The table shows the students' science motivation towards science learning in terms of science learning value, wherein the total mean and standard deviation (M=3.55, SD=0.932) were calculated and interpreted as "Agree". It means that the majority of the respondents understand the value of learning science as it can be used in daily lives, it can help them to solve problems, it can help them to experience inquiry activities and it satisfies their curiosity when they are learning science.

On the other hand, the respondents gave no opinion (M=3.39, SD= 1.10) about the value of learning science in stimulating their own thinking.

Table 4. Performance Goal

Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
1. I participate in science courses to get a good grade (-)	3.70	1.06	Agree
2. I participate in science courses to perform better than other students. (-)	2.79	0.990	No Opinion
3. I participate in science courses so that other students think that I'm smart (-)	2.43	1.06	Disagree
4. I participate in science courses so that the teacher pays attention to me. (-)	3.14	0.942	No Opinion
TOTAL	3.04	0.697	No Opinion

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)
2.61 – 3.40	No Opinion (NO)
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)

The table shows that student's motivation toward science learning in terms of performance goal. All items in this category are comprised of negative statements. The total mean score of (M=3.04) was interpreted as "No Opinion". It indicates that majority of the respondents have more neutral or mixed opinion regarding their performance goal. Also, it shows that the primary motivation for students in participating in science courses appears to be achieving a good grade. While the desire to appear smart to others such as their peers and teachers is not a significant motivator.

Table 5. Achievement Goal

Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
1. During a science course, I feel most fulfilled when I attain a good score in a test	4.08	0.943	Agree
2. I feel most fulfilled when I feel confident about the content in a science course	3.80	0.913	Agree
3. During a science course, I feel most fulfilled when I am able to solve a difficult problem.	3.89	0.970	Agree
4. During a science course, I feel most fulfilled when the teacher accepts my ideas.	3.79	1.06	Agree
5. During a science course, I feel most fulfilled when other students accept my ideas.	3.77	0.885	Agree
TOTAL	3.87	0.808	Agree

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)
2.61 – 3.40	No Opinion (NO)
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)

The table shows the students' motivation toward science learning in terms of achievement goal with a total mean score of (M=3.87) interpreted as "Agree", indicating that the majority of the respondents agreed that during science courses they feel confident and fulfilled when they attain good scores, know the content in science courses, being able to solve difficult problems, and teachers and peers accept their ideas.

Table 6. Learning Environment Stimulation

Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
1. I am willing to participate in this science course because the content is exciting and changeable.	3.53	1.03	Agree
2. I am willing to participate in this science course because the teacher uses a variety of teaching methods	3.43	0.996	Agree
3. I am willing to participate in this science course because the teacher does not put a lot of pressure on me	3.80	0.926	Agree

4. I am willing to participate in this science course because the teacher pays attention to me	3.46	0.998	Agree
5. I am willing to participate in this science course because it is challenging	3.44	0.885	Agree
6. I am willing to participate in this science course because the students are involved in discussions.	3.45	0.912	Agree
TOTAL	3.52	0.793	Agree

Legend:

Scale	Verbal Description
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)
2.61 – 3.40	No Opinion (NO)
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)

This table shows the Learning Environment Stimulation of students with a total mean score of (M=3.52) interpreted as “Agree”. This indicates that majority of the students are willing to participate in the science course because the content is exciting, changeable and challenging, the teacher uses a variety of teaching methods and does not apply any pressure on the science course and students are involved in the discussions.

Table 7. Total Mean of Science Academic Performance

	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Science Academic Performance	87	83.4	5.54	Satisfactory

Legend:

Grading Scale	Descriptor
90 – 100	Outstanding
85 – 89	Very Satisfactory
80 – 84	Satisfactory
75 – 79	Fairly Satisfactory
Below 75	Did Not Meet Expectations

The table shows the respondents’ science academic performance for the school year 2023-2024 with a mean score of (M=83.4). Based on the DepEd K-12 Grading System Step for Computing Grades, the calculated average science academic performance of the respondents can be interpreted as “satisfactory”.

Table 8. Correlational Analysis of SMTSL and Science Academic Performance

	Science Academic Performance		
	Pearson’s r	p-value	Interpretation
Self-efficacy	-0.092	0.398	Not Significant
Active learning strategies	0.358***	0.001	Highly Significant
Science learning value	0.318**	0.003	Significant
Performance goal	0.240*	0.025	Significant
Achievement goal	0.128	0.238	Not Significant

Learning environment stimulation	0.234*	0.029	Significant
SMTSL	0.270*	0.011	Significant

Note. * p < .05, **p < .01, ***p < .001

Based on the analysis of data, it was found out that students' motivation toward science learning and science academic performance have a significant relationship ($r = 0.270^*$; p -value = 0.011) it means that as the students' motivation toward science learning increases, their science academic performance will become higher and vice versa. Therefore, the null hypothesis will be rejected. Students who are motivated in learning science tend to have higher science academic performance. This result was supported by Rana et.al (2015), wherein the SMTSL overall scale and science achievement showed a strong positive relationship. Additionally, they asserted that motivation toward science learning can predict science achievement.

It also shows on the table that active learning strategies, science learning value, performance goals, and learning environment stimulation are all significantly correlated with science academic performance. This indicates that these factors are important for improving students' academic performance in science. On the other hand, self-efficacy and achievement goals do not show a significant correlation with science academic performance.

Program of Activities from the Results of the Study

The study reveals that in some items on students' motivation toward science learning in terms of active learning strategies, science learning value and learning environment stimulation received low mean score. Hence, the researchers offer the Program of Activities which is presented in Table 9.

Table 9. Proposed Program of Activities

Objectives	Action	Timeline	Persons Involved	Expected Outcome
Enhance students' learning strategies in science to construct new knowledge	Integrating follow-up questions to the topic allowing students to analyze and formulate an answer.	Year round S.Y. 2024-2025	Teacher, students, and researchers	The students develop active learning strategies in science and are able to construct new knowledge based on the previous understanding.
Increase students' thinking skills in learning science concepts.	Integrating questions about the lesson with a variety of question difficulty	Year round S.Y. 2024-2025	Teacher, students, and researchers	The students will develop higher critical thinking skills in learning science concepts

Inclusion of variety of teaching methods in science courses	Integrating Student-Centered Learning mainly focusing on students in giving the main idea and key points of the topic	Year round S.Y. 2024-2025	Teacher, students, and researchers	through science argument. The student's will be more motivated to pursue learning any science courses
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Conclusions

The study reveals that students have a positive belief in their capability to perform well in science. They express confidence in their understanding and performance in science-related tasks. When it comes to active learning strategies, the majority of the students utilized various learning strategies to construct new knowledge based on their previous understanding of science concepts. The overall pattern of responses in Table 3 indicates that students have a positive perception of the value of science learning, particularly in practical and curiosity-driven contexts. They recognize its usefulness and its role in providing meaningful and engaging learning experiences. The researchers also find out that students are primarily motivated by the desire to achieve good grades in science rather than by external factors such as their peers or other potential benefits of science learning. The researchers also indicate that students generally feel confident and fulfilled when they achieve good scores in science, have a solid understanding of the content, can solve difficult problems, and receive acceptance from teachers and peers for their ideas.

The students also perceive their science learning environment positively. They find the content exciting, changeable, challenging, and they appreciate the use of varied teaching methods of their teachers. This suggests that the diversity in teaching methods used by the teachers contributes to the students' engagement. Lastly, the positive correlation of SMTSL and science academic performance indicates that students who are more motivated to engage with science learning are likely to achieve higher performance in their science subjects. Motivation plays a crucial role in driving students to put more effort into their studies, which in turn enhances their academic outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the findings revealed in this study, it is recommended that teachers should continue to foster an environment that builds on students' confidence in their science capabilities and encourages the use of active learning strategies. This can be achieved by integrating real-world applications and problem-solving activities that spark curiosity and interest of the students, thus promoting a motivation alongside the desire for good grades. The use of diverse teaching methods should be expanded to cater different learning styles of the students, keeping the content exciting, challenging, and

relevant. Additionally, recognizing and rewarding not just academic performance but also effort, improvement, and deep understanding can further enhance students' motivation and engagement. Professional development opportunities for teachers such as seminars and workshop training to learn and share innovative strategies will also support these goals. Through implementing these recommendations, teachers can strengthen students' motivation in science learning and drive higher academic performance.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

A variety of ethical issues were taken into account to make sure that this study was carried out properly. Upon conducting the study, all respondents were informed of the goal of the study using the forms that were attached to the questionnaires, as well as their right to withdraw at any time while the data collection was being conducted. The researchers ensured the confidentiality of the data collected from every participant. They remained anonymous respondents in the study.

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